

Supplemental Material: Characterizing Delay and Control Traffic of the Cellular MME with IoT Support

Christian Vitale, *Member, IEEE*, Carla Fabiana Chiasserini, *Fellow, IEEE*,
Francesco Malandrino, *Member, IEEE*, and Senay Semu Tadesse, *Member, IEEE*

APPENDIX A PROOF OF PROPOSITION 1

The probability $f_{\alpha_q}(m|s=k)$ that source q visits state A , m slots after k can be computed as the multiplication of the probabilities of the following events:

- no transition into state A for $m-1$ slots;
- a transition into state A , exactly m slots after k .

If instead the last packet in the system was transmitted by q itself, $f_{\alpha_q}(m|s=k)$ can be computed as the multiplication of the probabilities of the following events:

- a transition from A to R (with probability 1) in slot $k+1$;
- no transition into state A for $m-2$ slots;
- a transition into state A , exactly m slots after k .

The probability $F_{\alpha_q}(m|s_q=k)$ for an MIoT that does not visit state A in slot k differs, compared to an MIoT visiting state A in slot k , only for the event in slot $k+1$. While for an MIoT that visits state A in slot k the event of returning in state R has probability 1, for an MIoT that does not visit state A in slot k the event of remaining in state R can be computed as 1 minus the probability of visiting A in slot $k+1$. Directly from (1), such probability is:

$$1 - \text{Beta}\left(\text{mod}(k+1, N) \frac{\delta}{T}\right) \frac{\delta}{T} \approx 1,$$

where the approximation holds if δ/T is small, i.e., if the number of slots in a period is large. This is a fair assumption, since the larger is the number of slots, the better is the matching between the MIoT model and the 3GPP aggregate traffic model.

APPENDIX B PROOF OF THEOREM 1

First, we substitute in (15) the CDF of the Erlang distribution, thus obtaining:

$$\begin{aligned} F_{\beta}(\tau) &= \sum_{z=1}^{\infty} \left[1 - \sum_{j=0}^{z-1} \frac{e^{-\lambda_{\alpha}\tau}}{j!} (-\lambda_{\alpha}\tau)^j \right] (1 - e^{-1})(e^{-1})^{z-1} \\ &= \sum_{z=1}^{\infty} (1 - e^{-1})(e^{-1})^{z-1} + \\ &\quad - \sum_{z=1}^{\infty} \sum_{j=0}^{z-1} \frac{e^{-\lambda_{\alpha}\tau}}{j!} (-\lambda_{\alpha}\tau)^j (1 - e^{-1})(e^{-1})^{z-1} \end{aligned}$$

where $\lambda_{\alpha} = Q/T$. We now solve the first summation, and invert the order of the two summations in the second term by exploiting the fact that $0 \leq j \leq z-1 < \infty$:

$$F_{\beta}(\tau) = 1 - \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \sum_{z=j+1}^{\infty} \frac{e^{-\lambda_{\alpha}\tau}}{j!} (-\lambda_{\alpha}\tau)^j (1 - e^{-1})(e^{-1})^{z-1}.$$

Next, we isolate and solve the summation over the index z :

$$\begin{aligned} F_{\beta}(\tau) &= 1 - \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \frac{e^{-\lambda_{\alpha}\tau}}{j!} (-\lambda_{\alpha}\tau)^j (1 - e^{-1}) \frac{(e^{-1})^j}{(1 - e^{-1})} \\ &= 1 - \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \frac{e^{-\lambda_{\alpha}\tau}}{j!} (-\lambda_{\alpha}\tau e^{-1})^j. \end{aligned}$$

Solving the summation over index j , allows us to prove the theorem, i.e., $F_{\beta}(\tau) = 1 - e^{-\lambda_{\alpha}\tau} e^{\lambda_{\alpha}\tau e^{-1}} = 1 - e^{-\lambda_{\alpha}(1-e^{-1})\tau}$.